

A comparative study of time of application between humic acid and organic matter on N transformation in soil

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Abstract : A laboratory investigation was carried out to monitor changes in different forms of N in soil treated with humic acid or organic matter 21 days before or on the day of start of the experiment. Results reveal that irrespective of treatments and stages of incubation, comparatively higher amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ and soluble NO_3^- is accumulated in soil treated either with FYM (Farm Yard Manure) or humic acid 21 days before than on the day of start of the experiment. Humic acid is decomposed faster than FYM leading to higher amount of accumulation of available N in humic acid treated system. Again, in general, irrespective of treatments, hydrolysable NH_4^+ increased over 120 days period of incubation and the amount of increase is more in soil treated either with FYM or humic acid on the day of start of the experiment. Amino acid and total hydrolysable organic N are more prone to N-mineralisation.

Keywords : Humic acid, FYM, different forms of N, N-mineralization.

Introduction

Nitrogen plays an important role in increasing agricultural production and since it is part of protein, its use may increase the food value of crops. Addition of organic matter as a source of nitrogen is well recognized¹ but direct application of humic acid as source of nitrogen to a soil has not been much studied in detail. It is now well established that N transformation in soil differs due to addition of either organic matter or humic acid². Therefore, it is of utmost importance to study N transformation in soils with respect to added organic matters. Addition of organic matter to soil before a cropping season is helpful in maintaining N pool in the field. Time of application of organic matter also influences the release of N from the organic source to a soil system. The role of humic acid in this regard is not clear and well known. Keeping the above information in view, the present research work was undertaken to study the effect of time of application of organic matter or humic acid on N-transformation in soil.

A laboratory experiment was conducted with the soil (Aquic *ustifluvent*) collected from the 0 to 15 cm depth of the field located in Pundibari block in the district of Cooch

Behar district, West Bengal, India. It is a sandy loam type of soil having pH 7.35, clay 3.4%, OC 0.91%, EC 0.114 mS cm^{-1} , exchangeable NH_4^+ 77.89 mg kg^{-1} , soluble NO_3^- 47.93 mg kg^{-1} , total nitrogen 982.34 mg kg^{-1} , total hydrolysable organic N 530.88 mg kg^{-1} , hydrolysable NH_4^+ N 176.96 mg kg^{-1} , available P_2O_5 132.82 kg ha^{-1} , available K_2O 114.00 kg ha^{-1} . The experiment was conducted in a completely randomized factorial design with three replications. The applications consist of farm yard manure (FYM) at 5 tons ha^{-1} , humic acid (HA) equivalent to FYM on the basis of N content and nitrogen as urea at 150 kg ha^{-1} . Humic acid was extracted from the FYM with 0.5 N NaOH following the method of Stevenson³. The nitrogen content of FYM and humic acid was 0.5 and 1.072 per cent, respectively. The treatments were as follows : T_1 = soil, T_2 = soil + N at 75 mg kg^{-1} , T_3 = soil + FYM at 2.5 g kg^{-1} , T_4 = soil + FYM at 2.5 g kg^{-1} + N at 75 mg kg^{-1} , T_5 = soil + HA equivalent to FYM on N basis, T_6 = soil + HA equivalent to FYM on N basis + N at 75 mg kg^{-1} . There were two sets of same treatments for two different times of application of organic matters. In the 1st set organic matter either FYM or humic acid was added 21 days

before the start of experiment. In the 2nd set FYM or humic acid was added on the day of start of the experiment. Nitrogen as urea at 75 mg kg^{-1} was added to all the N-treated systems as basal dose. Separate sets were maintained for identical collection of soil samples on 15th, 45th, 75th and 120th day of the experiment to analyze different forms of inorganic⁴ and organic⁵ N. Soils were maintained at 60% of water holding capacity and kept at room temperature ($26 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) throughout the experimentation period. The loss of water due to evaporation was replenished by periodic addition of sterile distilled water on every alternate day by difference in weight.

Data of inorganic and organic N as well as total N were statistically analyzed and critical difference were calculated at 5% level of significance to test the significance of means for the treatment difference¹¹.

The results showed that irrespective of treatments and stages of incubation, comparatively higher amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ is accumulated in soil treated either with FYM or humic acid 21 days before than on the day of start of experiment (Table 1). Furthermore, irrespective of treatments, exchangeable NH_4^+ tended to decrease up to 45th day, then increased up to 75th day and again decreased on 120th day in soils treated with either forms of organic matter 21 days before the start of incubation. However, application of FYM or humic acid on 0th day did not show similar trend of results (Table 2). Addition of FYM or humic acid 21 days before the actual cropping season significantly increased the exchangeable NH_4^+ in soil because of the time period received by the microorganisms for decomposing the organic matter and releas-

ing N from it⁶⁻⁹. The decrease and increase in exchangeable NH_4^+ in soil during the whole incubation period under different stages of organic matter addition is perhaps due to immobilization of exchangeable NH_4^+ ^{10,11} or loss of N due to denitrification¹² and or volatilization¹³ as well as mineralization of dead microorganisms and organic matter¹⁴.

Results further revealed that application of either FYM or humic acid on 21st day before the start of the experiment caused as accumulation of highest amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ on 15th day of the incubation. However, on the other hand, FYM or humic acid application on 0th day registered highest amount of exchangeable NH_4^+ on 45th day of the experiment. Critical examination of data in both the tables showed that the rate of N-mineralization was more or less of similar order.

Application of FYM or humic acid on 21st day before the start of the experiment accumulated highest amount of soluble NO_3^- on 75th day of incubation period. It is clear from the results (Table 1) that addition of either FYM or humic acid on 21st day before the start of the experiment caused an increase in exchangeable NH_4^+ with a concomitant decrease in soluble NO_3^- -N in soil¹⁵. Furthermore, application of FYM or humic acid on 0th day increased both the forms of exchangeable NH_4^+ and soluble NO_3^- in soil throughout the experimentation period. The results (Tables 1 and 2) thus clearly pointed out that addition of either forms of organic matter at least 3 weeks before the start of experiment leads to accumulate more amount of N in available form.

Table 1. Effect of application of FYM or humic acid at 21 days before the start of the experiment on changes in the amount (mg kg^{-1}) of exchangeable NH_4^+ , soluble NO_3^- and amino acid N in soil

Treatment	Incubation period (days)							
	15		45		75		120	
	NH_4^+	NO_3^-	NH_4^+	NO_3^-	NH_4^+	NO_3^-	NH_4^+	NO_3^-
T ₁	68.86	83.88	55.92	83.88	167.85	193.74	52.07	102.18
T ₂	99.86	119.83	69.9	137.81	85.88	251.67	60.1	141.25
T ₃	91.88	85.88	43.94	119.84	69.9	175.76	54.09	120.21
T ₄	199.73	115.84	43.94	175.76	97.86	303.62	60.1	162.28
T ₅	203.72	85.88	53.92	129.82	71.9	205.72	48.08	102.18
T ₆	211.7	112.83	59.92	153.79	73.9	237.68	51.09	150.26
Mean	145.96	100.69	54.59	133.48	94.55	228.03	54.26	129.73

T₁ : soil, T₂ : soil + nitrogen (urea @ 75 mg kg^{-1}), T₃ : soil + farm yard manure @ 2.5 g kg^{-1} , T₄ : soil + farm yard manure @ 2.5 g kg^{-1} + nitrogen (urea @ 75 mg kg^{-1}), T₅ : soil + humic acid, T₆ : soil + humic acid + nitrogen (urea @ 75 mg kg^{-1}).

Table 2. Effect of application of FYM or humic acid at 0th day of the experiment on changes in the amount (mg kg⁻¹) of exchangeable NH₄⁺, soluble NO₃⁻ and amino acid N in soil

Treatment	Incubation period (days)							
	15		45		75		120	
	NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻						
T ₁	31.96	63.91	71.9	159.78	48.08	105.18	48.08	123.21
T ₂	51.93	81.88	77.89	219.7	51.09	156.27	48.08	165.29
T ₃	33.95	65.91	89.88	163.78	39.07	96.17	36.77	126.22
T ₄	59.92	99.86	121.84	259.65	62.07	129.22	57.1	165.29
T ₅	59.91	45.92	103.86	195.74	51.09	93.16	48.08	105.18
T ₆	75.88	83.57	114.06	203.72	57.1	135.24	48.08	150.26
Mean	52.26	73.51	96.57	200.4	51.42	119.21	47.7	139.24

T₁ : soil, T₂ : soil + nitrogen (urea @ 75 mg kg⁻¹), T₃ : soil + farm yard manure @ 2.5 g kg⁻¹, T₄ : soil + farm yard manure @ 2.5 g kg⁻¹ + nitrogen (urea @ 75 mg kg⁻¹), T₅ : soil + humic acid, T₆ : soil + humic acid + nitrogen (urea @ 75 mg kg⁻¹).

Higher amount of total hydrolysable organic N is accumulated in soil treated with organic matter 21 days before the start of experiment upto 15th day of the incubation study (Figs. 1a and 1b). However, a reverse trend of results is observed after 15th day onwards to last stage

Fig. 1a. Changes in the amount of total hydrolysable organic N in soil treated with FYM or humic acid 21 days before the start of experiment.

Fig. 1b. Changes in the amount of total hydrolysable organic N in soil treated with FYM or humic acid on 0th day of the experiment.

Fig. 2a. Changes in the amount of total N in soil treated with FYM or humic acid 21 days before the start of experiment.

Fig. 2b. Changes in the amount of total N in soil treated with FYM or humic acid on 0th day of the experiment.

of the experiment. During this period comparatively higher amount total hydrolysable organic N is accumulated in soil treated either with FYM or humic acid on the day of start of experiment. It is clear from the results that mineralization of total hydrolysable organic N differs depending upon the time of addition of organic matter to a soil system. It further revealed that irrespective of N-treatment and time of addition of organic matters, humic acid is

more prone to mineralization than FYM particularly at the later period of incubation¹⁶. The effect of added inorganic N on accumulation of total hydrolysable organic N is noticeable throughout the investigation period^{17,18}.

The total amount of N in soil progressively decreased upto 45th day of the incubation (Figs. 2a and 2b). However, the amount of total N increased on 75th day but again decreased at the last stage of experiment. Soils treated with organic matter on the day of start of experiment did not show similar trend of results. The amount of total N increased on 45th, decreased on 75th and then increased on 120th day of the incubation study. The increase and decrease in total N in soils under both the treatments over the whole incubation period is due to release and fixation of non-exchangeable NH_4^+ in soils^{19,20}. It is interesting to note that total N decreased sharply from 15th to 120th day of incubation when soils are treated with either types of organic matter 21 days before the start of experiment. However, on the other hand, total N increased slightly from 15th to 120th day of incubation when soils are treated either with FYM or humic acid on the day of start of experiment. Results thus clearly showed that organic matters added 21 days before the start of experiment mineralized at a faster rate than FYM or humic acid applied on the start of experiment^{6,8}. The effect of added inorganic N is reflected on the data of N-treated systems at all the stages of incubation¹⁶.

Bulky FYM can be replaced by concentrated humic acid, particularly with respect to release of nitrogen from organic sources.

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